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Status of Oral Communication Skills in English Classes at Lian Senior High School

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the oral communication skills in English classes at Lian Senior High School. It aimed to determine the status of oral communication skills of Grade 11 students of Lian Senior High School. Moreover, it also aimed to find the different communication strategies that Grade 11 Students use in the classroom to improve their oral skills. Lastly, it covered the strategies that teachers use to develop the oral communication skills of Grade 11 students. As the output of this study, the researcher came up with a supplemental lesson in oral communication that would be used to reinforce the lessons they have already learned. This proposed intervention was called OralCom Supplemental Material in Oral English. The descriptive method of research was used with the questionnaire as the instrument. Twenty-one (21) teachers of Lian Senior High School were the participants of this study. Results revealed that 49 students obtained a grade of 81- 85, among 166 students, which can be seen as room for improvement. In learning to communicate, the students used different strategies such as using humor to engage the audience, using multiple modes of communication, active listening, asking for clarification, asking open-ended questions to gain insights, and conveying important points. Focusing on what others say and acknowledging it, maintaining awareness of body language and non-verbal cues, speaking clearly and concisely, and being mindful of the tone were also used. These strategies have been used by the students in the 11th grade and should be strengthened by the teachers. These strategies were the starting point of learning. All these activities can be done together or separately, depending on the objectives of the lesson. It is therefore recommended that this proposed intervention, called OralCom Supplemental Material in Oral English, be used for these students. The different strategies may also be continually used.

Keywords: *Oral Communication Skills, Communication Strategies, English Language Proficiency, Supplemental Learning Material*

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